

Overcoming difficulties in the evaluation of captan and folpet residues by supercritical fluid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry

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A B S T R A C T

Serious difficulties in evaluating the fungicides captan and folpet by the usual chromatography systems coupled to mass spectrometry are well known. These compounds are highly prone to degradation due to different conditions into tetrahydrophthalimide (THPI) and phthalimide (PHI). Such an effect can be produced at different stages of the analytical procedure or during the growing crop, making their evaluation troublesome. As a consequence, the quantification of captan and folpet is typically performed through or together these metabolites. However, imide ring metabolites can be produced by other unknown sources, including other phthalimide derived pesticides enabling false positive results. For this reason, in the last decade, laboratories demand a robust method to quantify captan and folpet, that overcomes such a situation. In the present work, various operational parameters were optimized to ensure the no degradation of captan and folpet facilitated by supercritical fluid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (SFC-MS/MS). A direct comparison with reverse-phase LC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS was conducted for comparative purposes. The representative commodities selected for this evaluation were pepper and tomato. Furthermore, possible oxidative degradation during the sample milling step was also evaluated and avoided by the application of crimmilling conditions and ascorbic acid addition. By the proposed procedure, captan and folpet were recovered in both matrices at the 84%–105% range and with an RSD below 8% at two concentration levels: 10 and 50 µg/kg. On the contrary, with GC-MS/MS, captan and folpet were not recovered, and, as a consequence, their evaluation was possible only by THPI and PI. In the case of LC-MS/MS a significant decrease in the sensitivity was observed compared to SFC-MS/MS. Other validation parameters evaluated were satisfactory. This new approach can assess the correct analysis of captan and folpet at low concentrations in fruits and vegetables.

1. Introduction

Captan is a fungicide that has been used since the decade of 1960 on a variety of crops [1]. Overexposure to this pesticide can induce potential reproductive toxic effects. Besides, its metabolite *cis*-1,2,3,6-tetrahydrophthalimide (THPI) may present a higher acute oral toxicity in comparison with captan following one of the last EFSA studies [2]. Folpet is also a fungicide that was evaluated for the first time in 1969 and since then has been reviewed several times because of its numerous formulations and crop applications. Folpet does not present high toxicity by the oral and dermal routes [3], however, if the subject is exposed to a high dose of this pesticide may pose direct risks for human health [4].

Nevertheless, the main problem is the involuntary overdose of these fungicides to animals like cattle and poultry [5]. Because of this, in 2013, EFSA published a reasoned opinion about the modification of the MRLs of captan in pome fruits and commodities of animal origin [6]. The cancer risk characterization of these compounds continues in controversy [7]. However, as captan and folpet are dicarboximides, they inhibit aldehyde dehydrogenase contributing to Parkinson's disease [8]. Captan (N-(trichloromethylthio)cyclohex-4-ene-1,2-dicarboximide) and folpet (N-(trichloromethylthio)phthalimide) have an imide ring in their structure connected to a trichloromethylthioside chain. Captan main metabolite is tetrahydrophthalimide (THPI), and folpet is phthalimide (PI) [9]. Hydrolysis and thiols reactions are the most common ways of degradation for these pesticides [10]. However, there are numerous chemical reactions that can produce the degradation of both pesticides into their imide ring metabolites like photooxidation [11] or wet air oxidation [12]. Furthermore, there are some enzymatic reactions that can degrade both compounds even to imide-based subproducts of their imide rings during subsequent reactions. Diverse research projects have demonstrated that acidic conditions reduce the aqueous hydrolysis of both compounds, increasing their stability approximately eight times in some scenarios [9,13].

From an analytical point of view, these pesticides are not easily amenable to be analyzed via liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry using an electrospray source (LC-ESI-MS/MS) due to a lack of sensitivity [10]. Furthermore, the analysis of captan and folpet is also problematic using gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (GC-MS/MS). These compounds tend to degrade to their imide-ring metabolites during the injection by GC-MS/MS. The percentage of degradation depends of the parameters set in the injector as well as the liner status. The use of alternative ionization sources in LC-MS/MS like atmospheric-pressure chemical ionization (APCI) can facilitate the analysis of these pesticides metabolites [14]. Regarding GC coupled to mass spectrometry, the analysis of captan and folpet can be improved using an on-column injection (OCI) [15] or negative chemical ionization (NCI) [16]. But, both approaches are difficult to apply in routine laboratories.

Analyzing high water content and low fat content fruits and vegetables; the most widely accepted methodology by laboratories is the standard QuEChERS multiresidue extraction and subsequent quantification of captan and folpet by their metabolites PI and THPI. However, there are many unknown sources of imide ring metabolites; indeed, some pesticides like phosmet are phthalimide-derived [17]. Some studies demonstrate the benefits of adding some extra clean-ups or extraction devices in the "classical" QuEChERS extraction method for the analysis of these compounds [18]. Many studies applied different procedures during the extraction like ultrasonication of the sample [19], dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction (DLLME) [20,21] and solid-phase extraction (SPE) [19,21].

The literature of captan and folpet analysis using supercritical fluid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (SFC-MS/MS) is almost non-existent. Nevertheless, some studies suggest the use of supercritical CO₂ extraction to prevent thermal degradation or hydrolysis [22]. It is accepted

that supercritical CO₂, in combination with methanol, is an acidic mobile phase [23], this fact could increase the stability of captan and folpet during the elution. From the theoretical point of view, these facts, combined with the ionization advantages of this type of chromatography [24], offer a good alternative for the analysis of these compounds highly prone to degradation.

The main objective of the present work was the use of the advantages offered by SFC in terms of low degradability conditions and high sensitivity to develop a robust method based on SFC for these fungicides. Different operational parameters were evaluated in the ESI source. Additionally, other approaches based on LC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS were compared for a better evaluation of the achievements. Sample preparation was also taken into consideration as a possible source of degradation. Both compounds were studied in terms of recoveries, linearity, reproducibility and matrix effect in tomato and pepper matrices.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and materials

The four pesticides of the study were provided by LGC (Teddington, United Kingdom) and manufactured by Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany). All the standards had a purity higher than 98% except for *cis*-1,2,3,6-Tetrahydrophthalimide (96.0%). The analytical standards were stored at -30 °C. The standard-mix solution was prepared using individual stock solutions (400 mg L⁻¹) of each standard and stored in the dark at -30 °C in amber glass vials. The solvent used for the stock solutions of captan and folpet was previously acidified with 0.4% of formic acid [10].

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) 5.3 quality was supplied by Abello Linde (Madrid, Spain), LC-MS quality Methanol used for mobile phase preparation was obtained from Fluka Analytical (Steinheim, Germany). The additives: ammonium formate and formic acid were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). The salts employed in the QuEChERS extraction (anhydrous magnesium sulphate, sodium chloride, sodium hydrogenocitrate sesquihydrate, and sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany) except for PSA that was obtained from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA). The L-Ascorbic acid used during the milling was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany).

2.2. Sample preparation

Two matrices (green pepper and tomato) were obtained from a local market in Almería (Spain). These matrices were extracted by a slightly modified QuEChERS without clean-up and analyzed to ensure that they did not have any detectable pesticide that could interfere with the study. The procedure followed for the extraction includes acidification of the acetonitrile with 1% of formic acid to increase the stability of captan and folpet. The final extract resulting from the extraction method contained 1 g of matrix per mL.

2.3. Vials preparation

Matrix-matched calibration curves were prepared by evaporating 100 µL of each blank extract under a gentle stream of nitrogen and reconstituted with the same volume of acetonitrile containing the mixture of the analyzed pesticides at the desired concentration. For the analysis of the spiked samples, 100 µL of each extract was introduced in a microvolume glass insert inside the vial.

2.4. SFC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS analysis

The SFC analysis was performed using a Nexera UC (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan). In addition to the standard devices of LC (binary pumps, column oven, and autosampler), this system is equipped with a CO₂ pump and a back-pressure regulator (BPR) splitless device just before the MS source.

Methanol with 1mM ammonium formate was used as a co-solvent (modifier) and mixed with the carbon dioxide during the gradient. The make-up solvent used after the column was methanol containing 5mM ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid. The make-up solvent was introduced in the system isocratically at 0.080 mL min⁻¹. The SFC separation was carried out on a C18 stationary phase column Shimpack UC-X RP (3µm, 250 × 2.1 mm). This column was acquired from Shimadzu Corporation. The oven temperature was set at 40 °C. The BPR pressure and temperature were established at 150 bar and 50 °C, respectively. The total flow used was kept constant at 1.3 mL min⁻¹. The gradient used during the analysis was as follows: an isocratic flow of 1% of modifier was kept for 2 min; the modifier percentage increased linearly to 4% at min 4 and increase to 8% at minute 8. After 1 min, the modifier percentage increase to 40%, and this condition was kept for 2 min. The modifier percentage was then reduced from 40 to 1% to recover initial conditions and maintained over 2 min.

The LC analysis was performed using the same system described below but avoiding the use of the CO₂ pump and the BPR. The mobile phase A was 98% water and 2% methanol, whereas mobile phase B was 98% methanol and 2% water, both mobile phases contained 5 mM ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid. The mobile phase gradient started with 100% of mobile phase A. It is reduced to 75% at minute 1.5 and 50% at minute 2.5. Mobile phase increase from this minute to minute 7.5 where it reaches 100% and is maintained for 2 min. At minute 11, initial conditions (100% of mobile phase A) are recovered and kept for 2 min for re-equilibration.

The SFC system is coupled to a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer 8060 (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan). The study was carried out employing an electrospray ionization source (ESI). The interface temperature was set at 125 °C, 125 °C for desolvation line, and 150 °C in the case of heat block. The interface voltage used was 4 kV. Regarding nebulizer, heating, and drying gas flows: 3 L min⁻¹, 10 L min⁻¹ and 10 L min⁻¹ were used, respectively.

2.5. Optimization of the SFC-MS/MS parameters

Captan, folpet, THPI, PI, and internal standards (dimethoate-d6, carbendazim-d3, malathion-d10, and dichlorvos-d6) were manually optimized using precursor ion search. For proper identification, two transitions must be detected with an ion ratio difference less than 30% and a retention time shift under 0.1 min [25]. Acquisition windows of ±0.35 min were established for each pesticide.

2.6. GC-MS/MS analysis

The analyses by gas chromatography were performed with an Agilent Intuvo 9000 GC coupled to an Agilent 7010 GC-MS/MS triple quadrupole and equipped with an Agilent 7693 autosampler. The samples were injected in splitless mode using a multimode injector through ultra inert inlet liners with glass wool (Agilent). A temperature ramp (80 for 0.1 min, then increased to 300 °C at 600 °C min⁻¹) was used in the injector and the total injection volume was 1 µL. The run time was 12.4 min, followed by 2.1 min for backflush (310 °C). The temperature program of the oven started at 60 °C (0.5 min), then it was increased to 170 °C (80 °C min⁻¹) and finally to 310 °C (20 °C min⁻¹). The flows were kept constant during the analyses (1.28 mL min⁻¹ for the first column and

1.48 mL min⁻¹ for the second column). Helium was employed as the carrier gas. The collision gas (nitrogen) flow was 1.5 mL min⁻¹, and the quenching gas (helium) flow was 2.25 mL min⁻¹. The high efficiency electron ionization source and the transfer line were kept at 280 °C during the analyses, and the quadrupoles were maintained at 150 °C.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Ionization in SFC-MS/MS vs LC-MS/MS

The reduction of the ion source temperatures has been demonstrated to be effective in increasing the sensitivity of captan and folpet [26]. A test of the ion source interface temperatures was performed, analyzing a mix with more than 230 pesticides through the same system using reverse phase LC and SFC. Only 2% of the compounds presented higher area values at the lower interface temperature tested (200 °C) using LC-MS/MS. However, with SFC-MS/MS, 42% of the pesticides were more sensitive at this low ion source temperature. It is a well-known fact that an increase of temperature in ESI is necessary to improve the desolvation of droplets in LC [27]. This fact demonstrates that the different ionization functioning of the SFC [24] allows to reduce the source temperatures and achieve greater sensitivity in many cases. As captan and folpet are pesticides that requires a huge reduction of the ion source temperatures to avoid degradation, SFC becomes a great choice for the analysis of these compounds.

It is a well-known fact that the low percentage of water in the mobile phase and the low solvent volume reaching the source due to the evaporation of CO₂ produce an increment of the sampling efficiency. This higher solvent evaporation rate had demonstrated to benefit the ionization of compounds like pyrethroids that usually are not analyzed by LC [28]. As with pyrethroids ionization, captan and folpet formed molecular ion ammonium adducts; both compounds share similar structures, and ammonium adduct ionization is related to the proton affinity and Lewis basicity of the compounds analyzed [29]. THPI metabolite of captan also ionizes with the molecular ion ammonium adduct. However, phthalamide metabolite (PI) of folpet is the one that presents the greater difficulty to be analyzed by SFC-MS/MS, only one transition can be detected and correspond to the protonated molecular ion. All the transitions used for these compounds are available in Table 1. Furthermore, we also found that the chromatographic gradient has a significant effect during the metabolite's ionization. A comparison between the same MS/MS platform coupled with LC and SFC after optimization was performed. The same vials were injected by SFC-MS/MS and reverse phase LC-MS/MS in the same system using identical ion source parameters. As can be observed in Fig. 1, folpet signal intensity was higher in SFC but there are no vast differences between both chromatographies. However, captan presented a huge difference in the peak intensity signal between LC and SFC. The intensity of the captan peak using SFC was more than seven times higher than with LC. As we previously checked with some compounds of the pesticide mix, these results suggest that SFC-MS/MS is more suitable analyzing thermally sensitive compounds.

Table 1

Retention times and mass spectrometer parameters for captan, folpet and tetrahydrophthalimide.

Compound	RT _{SFC} (min)	RT _{LC} (min)	Precursor <i>m/z</i>	Product <i>m/z</i>	Q1 Pre Bias(V)	CE	Q3 Pre Bias(V)
Captan	2,58	7,72	316,7	264	-23	-14	-28
Captan	2,58	7,72	316,7	299,9	-16	-7	-19
Captan	2,58	7,72	316,7	79,1	-30	-34	-15
Folpet	2,95	8,58	314,6	130,1	-23	-35	-23
Folpet	2,95	8,58	314,6	261,8	-17	-12	-30
Folpet	2,95	8,58	314,6	102	-16	-45	-17
THPI	6,73	1,29	168,9	81,1	-28	-23	-15
THPI	6,73	1,29	168,9	152,1	-25	-13	-29
THPI	6,73	1,29	168,9	79,1	-18	-30	-17

Fig. 1. Chromatograms of captan and folpet at the concentration of 100 µg/Kg in green pepper matrix using supercritical fluid chromatography and liquid chromatography (SFC and LC conditions described in experimental subsection). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

3.2. Ion source temperatures and gas flows

To achieve the best sensitivity and to avoid any thermal degradation, different ESI source temperatures were tested. Three temperature parameters of the ESI source are involved in the desolvation temperature of the interface. The different temperatures set and the related areas of captan and folpet are exposed in Table 2. T5 test corresponds to the temperatures applied to our multiresidue method of pesticides. As can be observed, there was a considerable increase in the area of the compounds when a decrease of temperature is being performed; however, below T2 temperatures, a decrease of sensitivity was observed. The temperatures set in T2 for the interface (125 °C), desolvation line (125 °C), and heat block (200 °C) were chosen for the final method. Ion source gas flows were also optimized: Drying gas (Nitrogen) and heating gas (Dry air). Four different flows were tested for each gas separately and both at the same time. Fig. 2 expresses the monitorization of the areas of both compounds during the various flows of gases. In the case of captan, there was a slight variation in the area during the different heating gas flows, being 10 L min⁻¹ the one that gives the higher area value. However, the differences were

higher when the different drying gas flows were tested. There was a vast decrease in the captan area when the lowest nitrogen flow tested was applied, being also 10 L min⁻¹ the one with a better result. The same flows were tested with folpet, and similar area values were obtained. Between 10 L min⁻¹ and 12 L min⁻¹ there were no huge differences. Finally, 10 L min⁻¹ was selected as the flow for the gases involved in the ionization of the compounds of study.

Table 2

Temperature tests for the determination of the optimal ion source values for captan and folpet.

Test	Interface (°C)	Desolvation line (°C)	Heat block (°C)	Captan area	Folpet area
T1	100	100	150	560458	35226
T2	125	125	150	856137	47925
T3	150	150	300	542891	44548
T4	200	200	300	270480	24589
T5	300	250	400	47995	8767

Fig. 2. Area values of captan and folpet applying different ion source gas flows.

3.3. Captan and folpet degradation during sample extraction

A modification of the QuEChERS methodology was applied to perform the extraction of the samples; the acetonitrile was acidified with 1% of formic acid, and no buffer salts or clean-up material were used to maintain the acidic pH of the solvent. Green pepper and tomato samples were fortified with captan/folpet at four different concentration levels (50, 100, 150 and 200 µg/kg). The 100 µg/kg point was extracted five times to check the reproducibility. When the milling of the

samples was performed without the addition of dry ice, captan and folpet cannot be detected even at the highest concentrations. When the extraction of green pepper samples was performed with cryogenic milling, both pesticides can be detected, but the recoveries were below 25% for captan and below 60% for folpet. Furthermore, the linearity/reproducibility of the four spiked samples did not fulfill the DG-SANTE requirements [25]. Hydrolysis and oxidation are common degradation processes that occur during the milling. It can be produced by enzymes naturally present and released during this process. For example, pectinases enzymes can degrade pectic substances through hydrolases [30,31]. These enzymes that produce the hydrolysis of pectin (pectinesterases) are present in sweet pepper during the different ripping stages [32]. Ascorbic acid is recognized as a competitive inhibitor of enzymes affecting browning properties [33-35]. We verify the effects of the use of ascorbic acid in combination with dry ice during the milling step. In green pepper matrix using 3% of ascorbic acid, an average recovery of 94% and 99% were obtained for captan and folpet respectively at 100 µg/kg, being 77% and 83% when 5% of ascorbic acid was added. The addition of L-ascorbic acid improves the recoveries of both compounds which are now inside the 70–120% range established by the DG-SANTE [25]. Furthermore, an RSD lower of 10% was obtained for both compounds in the five replicates studied. In the case of tomato, the recoveries at 100 µg/kg were very similar between the cryogenic extractions without ascorbic acid (75% captan, 84% folpet), with the addition of 3% of ascorbic acid (87% captan, 84% folpet) and with 5% of ascorbic acid (85% captan, 79% folpet). We can conclude that the benefits in applying ascorbic acid is matrix dependent as it was expected. The RSD was below 20% in all the cases for the five replicates.

3.4. Linearity

To perform the linearity study of captan and folpet, matrix matched calibration curves were prepared at five different concentration levels (10, 20, 50, 100, and 500 µg/kg) in green pepper and tomato matrices. The determination coefficients (r^2) of the calibration curves were higher than 0.999 for both pesticides in the two matrices studied. Furthermore, the back-calculated concentration deviations were lower than 20%. Through the experiment exposed in subsection 3.3 we checked that procedural standard calibration can be performed if cryogenic milling is performed with ascorbic acid in green pepper. The differences in the determination coefficients (r^2) and the RSD(%) of the response factor with and without ascorbic acid for procedural standard calibration curves can be observed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Linearity parameters of captan and folpet applying procedural standard calibration in green pepper with and without ascorbic acid addition. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

3.5. Matrix effect

The matrix effect reduction consequence of the mobile phase and the low flow reaching the source were explained numerous times in our previous studies. However, to achieve lower limits of quantification for these compounds, we are injecting a higher amount of sample (5 mg per injection). This fact seems to have a repercussion in matrix effects analyzing some matrices. For example, tomato matrix effects for captan and folpet were 47% and 107%, respectively. The captan result is considered a moderate matrix effect and the one of folpet is regarded as strong matrix effect. However, in green pepper matrix, the result for captan was 2%, being 18% for folpet. The results below 20% are considered low or non-existent matrix effect. For the vast majority of pesticides in our multiresidue method the matrix effects correspond to suppression of signal, but for these complex compounds the matrix effects correspond to an enhancement of the signal.

3.6. Recoveries and repeatability

After determining the appropriate extraction method for these compounds through the experiment performed in subsection 3.3, recovery studies at lower concentration levels were carried out. Captan and folpet were spiked in tomato and green pepper matrices at two different concentration levels: 10 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. The samples of tomato and green pepper were milled using dry ice and 3% of ascorbic acid. Three replicates of each concentration level were extracted following the modified QuEChERS previously described. The same extracts were injected using SFC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS. The recoveries are exposed in Fig. 4. Using SFC-MS/MS, captan and folpet were recovered in both matrices at the 84%–105% range and with an RSD below 8%. As captan and folpet were completely degraded in the liner during injection by GC, the compounds quantified were THPI and PI expressed as captan and folpet applying the residue

definition. The recoveries were in the 67%– 85% range, which were inside the acceptable limits. However, in the case of 10 µg/kg concentration level in tomato the RSD(%) was 35% and 56% for captan and folpet, respectively, which is outside the <20% requirement established in the DG-SANTE [25].

Fig. 4. Recoveries of captan and folpet using SFC-MS/MS and tetrahydrophthalimide and phthalimide recoveries analyzing the same samples by GC-MS/MS.

4. Conclusions

Supercritical fluid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry has shown better results analyzing captan and folpet comparing with reverse phase liquid chromatography. Ion source temperature below 200 °C is critical to get maximum sensitivity for these compounds. Both pesticides could be identified at 10 µg/kg in tomato and green pepper matrices by the proposed approach with the total absence of degradation to THPI or PI. The addition of dry ice and ascorbic acid during the milling step was critical to obtain good recoveries with some matrices. These compounds were evaluated in terms of linearity and reproducibility; results fulfilled DG-SANTE criteria in both cases. The matrix effects were quite high in the case of tomato matrix but virtually non-existent for green pepper. Despite the complexity of these compounds, a limit of quantification of 10 µg/kg was achieved in both matrices through SFC-MS/MS analysis.

CRediT author statement

Víctor Cutillas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Resources, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, Visualization. Florencia Jesús: Methodology, Validation, Investigation. Carmen Ferrer: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing. Amadeo Rodríguez Fernández-Alba: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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